

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D4.5 – Reporting on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>The identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in the UP2030 project is linked to the defined objectives and visions. The objectives and vision define the pilot profile, which filters the previously defined preliminary list of KPIs. Accordingly, a smaller list of KPIs for each pilot is defined. Ten lists of KPIs are defined that include KPIs related to the pilot's objectives; one list of KPIs for each pilot. This list is an input to be matched with the strategies to ensure the characteristics of KPIs, such as their relevance and measurability.</p>			

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Executive Summary

This report corresponds to a second version of the monitoring, evaluation, and pilot related Key Performance Indicator (KPI) validation in the 5UP-approach implementation report, extends the previous report. Several sections from the previous deliverable (D4.4) have been updated, and others have been added. This report aligns the KPI identification process with the UP2030 project activities involving defining objectives and vision formulation. These are considered base elements for identifying the KPIs. Each city in the UP2030 has identified several objectives have been identified to be achieved in the defined pilots. Based on the defined objectives and the drafting of the visions, a pilot profile for KPI identification is defined. Each pilot has a defined profile reflecting the output of the conducted workshops. This profile forms the base for identifying the KPIs to be measured.

Reflecting on the timeline, the validation of the KPIs was delayed to be able to align them with the objective and vision formulation. This delay ensures the alignment of the KPIs with the UP2030 project activities and processes undergoing in the pilots. The pilots are ahead of the prototype definition phase, in which strategies to achieve the objectives and visions are to be defined. The reformulation of the objectives, vision, and actions plays a role in identifying the KPIs to reflect on the possible changes and transformations in the pilots. For this purpose, a pre-defined list of KPIs for each pilot that is defined will be matched with the considered actions that clarify how to achieve the objectives during the next month. Accordingly, it is aimed to get confirmation on KPIs aligned with the action definition, that will comply with the UP2030 project progress.

This report presents the KPI identification alignment with the UP2030 project activities in Section 2, and the pilot profiles, reflecting the objectives and vision formulation found in Section 3. These profiles guide identifying the KPIs list for each pilot are found in Section 4.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package’s structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with the WP4 and WP2; UIC, R-Cities, and Benchmarking, Monitoring, KPIs Taskforce, as well as D4.2. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D2.2 – UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities 1	D4.6 – Report on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots 3
D2.3 – UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities 2	D4.7 – Report on strategic learning in city twinning programmes
D4.1 – UP2030 pilot implementation plan for the pilot cities 1	

<p>D4.2: UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities 2</p> <p>D4.4: Report on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots 1</p>	
<p>Mil.4: Cities have set-up LAAs</p> <p>Mil.5: Cities run first workshop on needs</p> <p>Mil.6: Cities run second workshop on vision</p>	<p>Mil.10: Cities run third workshop on Action</p> <p>Mil.13: All cities have at least one successful prototype</p> <p>Mil.14: Cities run fourth workshop on upscale</p>

The target groups of this report are the Pilot Cities and City Liaisons as well as the technical partners (R-Cities, TSPA, BH, DRAXIS). The main beneficiaries of this deliverable will be taskforce leaders related to implementation of methods and their assessment as well as project coordinators. Some parts of this report are based on the contact with Pilot Cities and City Liaisons, and the further versions of this report analyze the impact of implemented methods on the pilot cities. Thus, input from Pilot Cities and City Liaisons is needed during the project’s lifetime. The report is to be shared with the project coordinators, WP4, and Pilot Cities and City Liaisons.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
BH	Buro Happold GMBH
D	Deliverable
DRAXIS	DRAXIS Environmental S.A.
GenALisbon	General Assembly Lisbon
ICT	Internet and Communication Technology Infrastructure
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
Mil	Milestone
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning & Architecture
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

This deliverable is a part of the work done in WP4 that is concerned with the pilot implementation and evaluation (UP-Grading). As a part of this work package, this deliverable builds on the work done in Deliverable 4.4 (D4.4 - Report on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots 1) that defined the key performance indicators (KPIs) monitoring and evaluation process and extended this process in detail. This process should be aligned with the UP2030 project activities and the workshops planned by the TSPA. The defined process depends on cities' objectives, visions, and selected actions (strategies). Based on the set objectives, actions are selected to realize the defined vision and achieve the objectives. The definition of the KPIs is challenging due to the differences between pilots, their objectives, and the selected actions. This leads to making this process an iterative process to ensure that the defined KPIs reflect the UP2030 project and the pilots and are measurable.

Validating the KPIs is a fundamental step before adopting them. Thus, the KPIs identification process focuses on matching the defined KPIs with the UP2030 project activities before seeking approval from the cities and their liaisons. As a step in the validation process, the KPIs are broken down into needed variables to be collected, making it easier to understand the relation between the KPIs and the impacted areas by the actions, as well as enabling an easier evaluation of the ability to collect the data related to these KPIs. The data forms the base for quantifying the KPIs and assigning them a value. The variables could be in the form of a numerical value or a Likert scale. The Likert scale measures opinions and perceptions. A scale with five points is used: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. Accordingly, KPIs are quantified to be used in the monitoring process.

The KPIs evaluate the implementation of the actions and the achievements of the set objectives. Thus, KPIs quantifies the achievements to ease the monitoring of the changes resulting from the implementation of actions. The change in a KPI reflects the impact of implemented actions.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable focuses on aligning the UP2030 project activities with the KPIs identification process and matching it with the prototype definition. Cities and their liaisons are undergoing several activities in the UP2030 project to define objectives to be achieved, formulate visions, and define actions to be implemented by selecting strategies. These activities form the base for the identification of the KPIs. Accordingly, the KPIs identification evolves.

Objectives were set, and visions were formulated; thus, initial KPIs reflecting these objectives were defined. The finalization of the KPIs definition depends on the definition of the adopted strategies (selected actions) that specify progress to achieve the objective in the context of the UP2030 project. This finalization is not included in this deliverable.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organized as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 – Aligning KPIs Identification and UP2030 Activities: The UP2030 activities are linked to the objective definition, vision formulation, and prototype definition.

- ❖ Section 3 — Pilot Profiles based on Objectives and Visions: The formulated visions and objectives define the pilot profiles, which consist of several dimensions related to urban planning and design.
- ❖ Sections 4 – Identified List of KPIs: Selected KPIs based on defined profiles are presented.
- ❖ Section 5: – Conclusions and Next Steps: This section summarizes the outcome of this deliverable and provides an overview of the next steps.

2 Aligning KPIs Identification and UP2030 Activities

In the context of the UP2030 project, several workshops and activities have been conducted to facilitate the identification of pilots' objectives, visions, and methods selection. The output of these activities is linked to the identification process of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were defined in D4.4 and depicted in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the updated timeframe associated with the monitoring process. The output of the carried activities in the UP2030 project facilitates the input to the identification process of KPIs. The definition of pilot profiles and derived KPIs are linked to these activities' outputs. Accordingly, the link with project activities is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1: KPI monitoring process

Figure 2: The link between KPI identification and the UP2030 activities

The identification of the pilot profiles is based on the cities' storylines, objectives, and vision formulation. These were identified in several workshops arranged with cities (such as Mil5 (Cities run first workshop on needs) and Mil6 (Cities run second workshop on vision)). The output of these workshops defines the pilots' current state and the future picture to be achieved. Based on the difference between the current state and the future picture, actions should be taken to achieve this transformation. The action is facilitated through several adapted methods, forming a prototype. Each pilot adapts several actions to achieve its set objectives. These actions influence the KPI identification. Thus, the KPIs should match these defined actions to reflect on the possible changes and transformations occurring in the pilots.

In this context, a matrix is defined to relate the objectives and strategies to be implemented by the pilots. This matrix arranges them tabulated and facilitates a tool to relate the strategies to KPIs. These KPIs are to be selected from the preliminary list of KPIs. Some of these KPIs are related to the realization of the selected strategies, and others are related to the definition of the prototypes during the project run.

The validation of the identified KPIs is a fundamental step to ensure the measurability of the KPIs, and it is a way of communicating these KPIs to the cities and their liaisons. Once the KPIs are identified, the KPI measuring timeframe is set. KPIs are measured once they are set, and this value is called the As-Is state, which pictures the current status of the pilot before the implementation of actions. Depending on the KPIs, its next measurement will be scheduled and planned. On the one hand, if the KPI is related to the realization of the actions, the KPIs can be measured after the realization starts. These KPI values could be predicted using simulation models. On the other hand, the other KPIs related to the planning of the prototype and up-scaling it are measured during the project run.

The KPI analysis is not limited to the comparison of KPIs values to the As-Is ones to draw conclusion. It can involve the prediction of KPI values as demonstrated in Figure 3. The predicted trend for KPI values is based on historical collected values. This trend indicates the possible KPI values in the future, along with a confidence interval. A great deviation from this trend triggers the need for corrective actions that is included in continuous reporting.

Figure 3: Prediction of KPIs values and their monitoring

3 Pilot Profiles based on Objectives and Visions

This section illustrates the defined profile in reference to the defined profiles in D4.4. According to the visioning and objective workshops, the defined objectives are explored to define the profiles as illustrated in Table 1 and Table 2. Exploring these profiles highlights the focus on the different dimensions of urban planning and design. The pilots' focus varies depending on their vision and the set objectives, and the summary of their focus is illustrated in Table 3.

Table 1: Pilot profiles for cities: Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul and Lisbon

Dimension	Category	Belfast	Budapest	Granollers	Istanbul	Lisbon
Economy	Internet and Communication Technology Infrastructure (ICT)					✓
	Water Sanitation					✓
	Drainage			✓		✓
	Waste					✓
	Electricity Supply					
	Transport	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Public Sector		✓		✓	✓
	Innovation	✓		✓		
	Employment	✓		✓	✓	
	Buildings		✓	✓	✓	✓
	Urban Planning	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Environment	Air Quality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Water Sanitation					✓
	Environmental Quality	✓		✓		✓
	Energy			✓	✓	✓
Society and culture	Education					✓
	Health					✓
	Culture					
	Housing			✓		
	Social Inclusion			✓		
	Safety					
	Food Security					
Governance	Organization		✓	✓	✓	✓
	Community Involvement	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Multi-level Governance	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Propagation	Scalability and Replicability	✓	✓	✓		✓
	Factor of Success					

Table 2: Pilot profiles for cities: Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb

Dimension	Category	Milan	Muenster	Rotterdam	Thessaloniki	Zagreb
Economy	ICT				✓	
	Water Sanitation					
	Drainage		✓			
	Waste					
	Electricity Supply					
	Transport		✓			✓
	Public Sector					✓
	Innovation					✓
	Employment				✓	✓
	Buildings				✓	✓
	Urban Planning	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Environment	Air Quality	✓		✓	
Water Sanitation						
Environmental Quality			✓	✓		✓
Energy			✓		✓	✓
Society and culture	Education			✓		
	Health					✓
	Culture			✓		
	Housing		✓	✓	✓	✓
	Social Inclusion		✓	✓	✓	✓
	Safety					
	Food Security					
Governance	Organization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Community Involvement		✓	✓	✓	✓
	Multi-level Governance	✓	✓	✓		
Propagation	Scalability and Replicability	✓	✓	✓		
	Factor of Success		✓			

Referring to Table 3, most of the pilots focus on “urban planning”, “community involvement”, and “organization” to be achieved during the UP2030 project. Additionally, pilots aim to achieve other changes and transformations. These pilot profiles are defined according to the revision of the cities’ storylines, objectives, and vision. Thus, they should be validated by the cities and their liaisons. In addition, these categories could include KPIs related to the realization of the selected actions or the planning of the prototype.

Table 3: Summary of pilot profiles

Dimension	Category	Number of interested pilots	Interested pilots
Economy	ICT	2	Lisbon, Thessaloniki
	Water Sanitation	1	Lisbon
	Drainage	3	Granollers, Lisbon, Muenster
	Waste	1	Lisbon
	Electricity Supply	0	
	Transport	7	Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Muenster, Zagreb
	Public Sector	4	Budapest, Istanbul, Lisbon, Zagreb,
	Innovation	3	Belfast, Granollers, Zagreb
	Employment	5	Belfast, Granollers, Istanbul, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki
	Buildings	7	Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb
Urban Planning	9	Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb	
Environment	Air Quality	7	Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Rotterdam,
	Water Sanitation	1	Lisbon
	Environmental Quality	6	Belfast, Granollers, Lisbon, Muenster, Rotterdam, Zagreb
	Energy	6	Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Muenster, Thessaloniki, Zagreb
Society and culture	Education	2	Lisbon, Rotterdam
	Health	2	Lisbon, Zagreb
	Culture	1	Rotterdam
	Housing	5	Granollers, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb
	Social Inclusion	5	Granollers, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb
	Safety	0	
	Food Security	0	
Governance	Organization	9	All except Belfast
	Community Involvement	9	All except Milan
	Multi-level Governance	8	Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam,
Propagation	Scalability and Replicability	7	Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam,
	Factor of Success	1	Muenster

4 Identified List of KPIs

Referring to D4.4, identifying KPIs is based on several criteria: relevance to objectives and quantifying these objectives, completeness, accessibility in terms of data availability, clarity of KPI definition and data collection, understandability of the KPIs by stakeholders and project members, measuring unique aspects of the UP2030 project's impact, and autonomy of the KPIs. The identified KPIs are classified as Core and Pilot Specific.

4.1 List of Core KPIs .

As illustrated in D4.4, Core KPIs were broken down into needed variables to be collected. This step ensures that the identified KPIs are measurable (accessible regarding data availability). According to the feedback received in the General Assembly Lisbon (GenALisbon) workshop, Table 4 illustrates whether data can be collected at the pilot area level or the city-wide level, and the data collection frequency, i.e., once, annually, every half year or quarterly. From the feedback, the following points are raised:

- The cities can collect data related to cities, not pilots, for most variables.
- Some of the variables could be collected yearly. In the feedback, few cities showed the capability to record the variable values more frequently.

From Table 4, the measuring capabilities force the definition of approaches to deal with KPIs measured for whole cities when they cannot be measured for the pilot. The changes taking place in the pilots cannot be directly reflected on changes in the whole cities.

It is worth mentioning that most of the considered KPIs are related to the realization of the actions.

Table 4: Summary of feedback collected in GenALisbon workshop

Variable	Place		Time	
	Pilot	City	Once	Yearly
Population	5	8	3	6
Length travelled by public transportation	5	6	2	4
Pedestrian areas	5	5	3	4
Total green areas	5	7	4	2
Total length of streets	5	5	5	1
Total area of the pilot or city	7	7	6	1
Total length of streets of active mobility	5	6	2	4
Total length of streets controlled by ICT	0	4	2	0
Total number of low-emission vehicles	0	5	1	4
Total number of vehicles	3	4	2	4
Total mixed-use area	4	3	5	1
Total number of buildings	5	6	5	2
Total energy efficient buildings	2	2	2	0
Total electricity consumption	3	6	0	6
Total energy consumption from renewable sources	1	4	0	4
Total emissions of tons of CO2	1	7	1	4
Average concentration of pollutants	2	5	1	2
Percentage of total solid waste recycled	1	6	0	5
Kilos of total waste	0	6	0	5
Number of violent crimes	1	6	0	6
Social Polarization	0	3	1	2

4.2 [List of Specific KPIs](#)

Drawing from the work outlined in D4.4, a preliminary list of KPIs is defined to select Pilot Specific KPIs from it later. This preliminary list consists of KPIs found in literature and practice (D4.4, City Resilience Index, Parmenter (2015), Selection of key performance indicators (KPIs) in the transition towards low-carbon urban communities, Smart City performance measurement system, Smart zero carbon city readiness level, Sustainable Cities, Wollman (2022), Luijer (2021)). Referring to Section 3, a profile is defined for each pilot based on the objectives and city storylines. These profiles are utilized to filter the preliminary list of KPIs for each pilot in the UP2030 project. An example of these KPIs is shown in Table 5, in which KPIs for the Belfast profile are listed. This list of KPIs is preliminary to be confirmed by the cities and their liaisons and is constructed based on the defined profile. Referring to Figure 2, the definition of strategies (and actions) will redefine the KPIs to select those KPIs that are relevant and measurable. Thus, the future definition of actions to be considered by the cities indicates the definition of the KPIs to be included and considered for the measurement.

Table 5: Specific KPIs assigned to Belfast

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal-controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitant] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travelers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travelers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
Innovation	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises	Calculate as: [Number of SMEs / Total number of enterprises] *100
	Diverse economic base	Calculate as: Inverse of the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) of industrial concentration, where lower values indicate greater diversification
Employment	Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed / Total city-related labor force] *100
Buildings	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitants

	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitalized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements) --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No.
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants.
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants.
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants.
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No.
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement-Financial support	Likert scale.
	Smart city policy	Likert scale.
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No.
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale.
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale.
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale.
	Ease of use for professional stakeholders	Likert scale.
	Trialability	Likert scale.
	Advantages for end users	Likert scale.
	Advantages for stakeholders	Likert scale.
	Visibility of Results	Likert scale.

	Solution(s) to development issues	Likert scale.
	Effective co-ordination with other government bodies	Likert scale.

In addition to validating the defined KPI list, the timeframe of their measurement should be specified. Some of these KPIs might be measured at the beginning and end of the project or more frequently. The KPIs values measured before implementing the defined actions (strategies) represent the As-Is state (the start state). Other KPI values are measured during the project run depending on the type of actions and expected impact. By comparing the new KPIs values and the As-Is values, the actions impact is evaluated. However, some of these KPIs might not encounter a change resulting from the action during the UP2030 project run (until the end of the project). Thus, these KPIs' forecasts will be planned based on simulation and prediction models. These KPI values will be measured after the UP2030 project and compared to the predicted ones to record any deviations.

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable illustrates and matches the UP2030 project activities' KPI identification to the activities. This process aims to align the KPI identification with the activities, allowing for the validation of the selected KPIs and ensuring their alignment with the UP2030 project ambitions, city visions, and the capability of their measurement. These KPIs define a monitoring system to track the impact of action taken. Depending on the KPIs, some prediction and simulation models could be used to predict them.

The pilot profiles are defined based on the updates in the UP2030 activities. Following this step, the KPIs are derived to align with the pilots' objectives and visions.

As a next step, the KPIs will be matched with defined actions (strategies). In addition, the list of KPIs will be updated according to the defined actions in the next weeks/ months. Then, the cities and their liaisons will validate the KPIs. This validation guarantees that the KPIs are relevant and aligned with the UP2030 project ambitions as well as measurable. Additionally, the classification of KPIs, such as which ones to measure and which to predict, is to be decided. The measurement of the KPIs to be measured will be scheduled and planned. The rest of the KPIs will be included in a monitoring framework for pilots to use after the realization of the actions.

Data collection for KPIs to measure is to be performed, starting with data analysis and reporting to facilitate the monitoring of these KPIs. The reports provide insights to guide city decision-making regarding the adopted methods to achieve the cities' vision; monitoring these KPIs will play a pivotal role in assessing the impact of proposed initiatives or methods and driving positive urban transformation. Additionally, cities could further track these KPIs after the project duration to study their evolution after the UP2030 project.

References

- City Resilience Index - Arup. (n.d.). www.arup.com/perspectives/publications/research/section/city-resilience-index, last access on 28 November 2023.
- Parmenter, D. (2015). Key performance indicators: developing, implementing, and using winning KPIs. John Wiley & Sons.
- Selection of key performance indicators (KPIs) in the transition towards low-carbon urban communities. (n.d.). https://www.eceee.org/library/conference_proceedings/eceee_Summer_Studies/2019/5-smart-and-sustainable-communities/selection-of-key-performance-indicators-kpis-in-the-transition-towards-low-carbon-urban-communities/, last access on 28 November 2023.
- Smart City performance measurement system | CITYKEYS | Project | Fact sheet | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission. (n.d.-a). <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/646440>, last access on 28 November 2023.
- Smart zero carbon city readiness level: - REVISTA DE INGENIERIA DYNA. (n.d.). <https://www.revistadyna.com/busqueda/smart-zero-carbon-city-readiness-level-sistema-de-indicadores-para-diagnostico-de-ciudades-en-su-cam>, last access on 28 November 2023.
- Sustainable Cities, S. (n.d.). Collection methodology for key performance indicators for smart sustainable cities united smart sustainable cities 4 Montevideo office collection methodology for key performance indicators for smart sustainable cities ii foreword.
- Wollman, David. Smart Cities and Communities: A Key Performance Indicators. 2022.
- Luijter, G. (2021). World Benchmarking Alliance Just Transition Methodology-July 2021.

APPENDIX: Pilots KPIs

Table 6: Specific KPIs assigned to Budapest

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travelers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travelers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
Public Sector	Comprehensive hazard and exposure mapping	Calculate as: The number of hazards included in the mapping (e.g., flooding, earthquakes, chemical spills).
	Open Data	Calculate as: [Total number of open datasets published / Total number of datasets] *100
	e-Government	Calculate as: Number of public services available through online services

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as: [Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car-free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitant
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living within 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements) --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (µg) / volume of air sampled (m3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tones CO2) / Total number of city inhabitants
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement-Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale
	Ease of use for professional stakeholders	Likert scale
	Trialability	Likert scale
	Advantages for end users	Likert scale
	Advantages for stakeholders	Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Visibility of Results	Likert scale
	Solution(s) to development issues	Likert scale
	Effective co-ordination with other government bodies	Likert scale

Table 7: Specific KPIs assigned to Granollers

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travelers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travelers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as:[Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: $[\text{Total area of pedestrian/car free zones} / \text{Total city area}] * 100$
	Green areas	Calculate as: $[\text{Total green area} / \text{Total city area}] * 100$ or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitants
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: $[\text{Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha} / \text{Number of city inhabitants}] * 100$
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements) --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (μg) / volume of air sampled (m^3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tones CO_2) / Total number of city inhabitants
Environmental Quality	EMF Exposure	Calculate as: $[\text{Number of sites complying with WHO guidelines} / \text{Total number of sites}] * 100$
	Noise Exposure	Calculate as: $[\text{Number of city inhabitants exposed to noise levels [LDEN (day-evening- night)] over 55 dB(A)} / \text{Total city inhabitants}] * 100$
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: $[\text{Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr)} / \text{Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)}] * 100$
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: $[\text{Total energy consumption from fossil fuels} / \text{Total energy consumption}] * 100$
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m^2)
organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in the implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement- Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale
	Ease of use for professional stakeholders	Likert scale
	Trialability	Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Advantages for end users	Likert scale
	Advantages for stakeholders	Likert scale
	Visibility of Results	Likert scale
	Solution(s) to development issues	Likert scale
	Effective co-ordination with other government bodies	Likert scale

Table 8: Specific KPIs assigned to Istanbul

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travelers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travelers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
Public Sector	Comprehensive hazard and exposure mapping	Calculate as: The number of hazards included in the mapping (e.g., flooding, earthquakes, chemical spills).
	Open Data	Calculate as: [Total number of open datasets published / Total number of datasets] *100
	e-Government	Calculate as: Number of public services available through online services
Employment	Creating and providing or supporting access to green and decent jobs for an inclusive and balanced workforce in companies and organizations	Yes / No

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Retaining and re- and/or up-skilling workers for an inclusive and balanced workforce	Yes / No
	Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed / Total city-related labor force] *100
	Youth Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed youth/ Total city-related youth labor force] *100
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as:[Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitant
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements) --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (µg) / volume of air sampled (m3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tones CO2) / Total number of city inhabitants
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: [Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr) / Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)] *100

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: [Total energy consumption from fossil fuels / Total energy consumption] * 100
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m2)
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement- Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No

Table 9: Specific KPIs assigned to Lisbon

	KPI	Measuring methodology
ICT Infraestructure	Household Internet Access	Calculate as: [Number of households with internet access / Total number of households] *100
	Fixed Broadband Subscriptions	Calculate as: [Number of fixed broadband subscriptions / Total number of households] *100
	Wireless Broadband Subscriptions	Calculate as: Number of wireless broadband subscriptions / one 100,000th of the city's population
	Wireless Broadband Coverage	Calculate as: Area of city covered by mobile services (km2) / Total area of the city (km2). Each service should be reported on separately
	Availability of WIFI in Public Areas	Calculate as: Total number of WIFI hotspots provided by the city administration (excluding commercial entities)
Water and Sanitation	Smart Water Meters	Calculate as: [Number of smart water meters installed / Total number of water meters installed] *100
	Water Supply ICT Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of system monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of total system (km)] *100
	Basic Water Supply	Calculate as: [Number of city households with access to basic water sources / Total number of city households] *100
	Potable Water Supply	Calculate as: [Number of city households with a safety managed drinking water / Total number of city households] *100
	Water Supply Loss	Calculate as: [Volume of water supplied minus the volume of utilized water (l/year) / Total volume of water supplied (l/year)] *100
	Wastewater Collection	Calculate as: [Number of households served by wastewater collection / Total number of households] *100
	Household Sanitation	Calculate as: [Total number of city households with access to basic sanitation and facilities / Total number of city households] *100
Drainage	Drainage / Storm Water System ICT Monitoring	Calculate as: [Length of system monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of total system (km)] *100
	Inclusive access to safe drinking water	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to safe drinking water / Total city population] *100
Waste	Municipal waste rate	Calculate as: Kilos per person.
	Municipal solid waste recycling rate	Calculate as: % of municipal solid waste that is recycled with respect to the total.
	Solid Waste Collection	Calculate as: [Number of city households that are served by solid waste collection / Total number of city households] *100

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travellers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travellers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
Public Sector	Comprehensive hazard and exposure mapping	Calculate as: The number of hazards included in the mapping (e.g., flooding, earthquakes, chemical spills).
	Open Data	Calculate as: [Total number of open datasets published / Total number of datasets] *100
	e-Government	Calculate as: Number of public services available through online services
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as:[Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (µg) / volume of air sampled (m3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tonnes eCO2) / Total number of city inhabitants
Environmental Quality	EMF Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of sites complying with WHO guidelines / Total number of sites] *100
	Noise Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants exposed to noise levels [LDEN (day-evening- night)] over 55 dB(A) / Total city inhabitants] *100
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: [Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr) / Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)] *100
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: [Total energy consumption from fossil fuels / Total energy consumption] * 100
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m2)
Education	Student ICT Access	Calculate as: [Students with classroom access to ICT facilities / Total number of students enrolled in schools] *100
	School Enrolment	Calculate as: [Number of students in primary and secondary levels in public and private schools / Total number of the school aged population] *100
	Higher Education Degrees	Calculate as: Number of city inhabitants holding at least one higher level education degree / One 100,000th of the city's population.

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Adult Literacy	Calculate as: [Number of adult city inhabitants who are deemed to be literate / Total number of city inhabitants'] *100
Health	Electronic Health Records	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants with electronic health records / Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Life Expectancy	Calculate as: Average number of years that a newborn is expected to live if current mortality rates continue to apply.
	Maternal Mortality Rate	Calculate as: Number of maternal deaths per year / One 100,000th of live births per year.
	Physicians	Calculate as: Number of general or specialized physicians working in the city (FTE) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	In-Patient Hospital Beds	Calculate as: Total number of in-patient hospital beds (public and private) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Health Insurance /Public Health Coverage	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants covered by health insurance or a public health system / Total city inhabitants] *100
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
Just transition planning	Likert scale	
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement- Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale
	Ease of use for professional stakeholders	Likert scale
	Trialability	Likert scale
	Advantages for end users	Likert scale
	Advantages for stakeholders	Likert scale
	Visibility of Results	Likert scale
	Solution(s) to development issues	Likert scale
	Effective co-ordination with other government bodies	Likert scale

Table 10: Specific KPIs assigned to Milano

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: $[\text{Total area of pedestrian/car free zones} / \text{Total city area}] * 100$
	Green areas	Calculate as: $[\text{Total green area} / \text{Total city area}] * 100$ or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitants
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: $[\text{Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha} / \text{Number of city inhabitants}] * 100$
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements) --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (μg) / volume of air sampled (m^3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tones CO_2) / Total number of city inhabitants
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement- Financial support	Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No

Table 11: Specific KPIs assigned to Muenster

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Drainage	Drainage / Storm Water System ICT Monitoring	Calculate as: [Length of system monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of total system (km)] *100
	Inclusive access to safe drinking water	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to safe drinking water / Total city population] *100
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.)
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travelers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travelers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit.
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles
Environmental Quality	EMF Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of sites complying with WHO guidelines / Total number of sites] *100
	Noise Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants exposed to noise levels [LDEN (day-evening- night)] over 55 dB(A) / Total city inhabitants] *100
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: [Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr) / Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)] *100
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: [Total energy consumption from fossil fuels / Total energy consumption] * 100
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m2).
Housing	Informal Settlements	Calculate as: [Number of people living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Expenditure on Housing	Calculate as: [Expenditure on Housing (USD) / Total household income (USD)] *100
Social Inclusion	Gender Income Equality	Calculate as: Average hourly earnings of female employees (USD) / Average hourly earnings of male employees (USD)
	Gini Coefficient	Calculate as: Area between 45 degree line and Lorenz curve / Entire area below 45 degree line

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Poverty Share	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants living below the poverty line / Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Child Care Availability	Calculate as: [Number of day-care spots available for pre-school children / Total number of pre-school age children] *100
	Access to electricity	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to electricity / Total population] *100
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement- Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale
	Ease of use for professional stakeholders	Likert scale
	Trialability	Likert scale

Table 12: Specific KPIs assigned to Rotterdam

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Employment	Creating and providing or supporting access to green and decent jobs for an inclusive and balanced workforce in companies and organizations	Yes / No
	Retraining and re- and/or up-skilling workers for an inclusive and balanced workforce	Yes / No
	Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed / Total city-related labor force] *100
	Youth Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed youth/ Total city-related youth labor force] *100
	Tourism Industry Employment	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related employees-Tourism Sector / Total city-related labor force] *100
	ICT Sector Employment	Calculate as: [Number of employees ICT sector / Number total city labor force] *100
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as:[Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitant

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements). --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Air Quality	Air Pollution	Calculate as: Mass of pollutant collected (μg) / volume of air sampled (m^3). Report as annual mean concentration for each pollutant.
	GHG Emissions	Calculate as: Total GHG emissions (Tones CO ₂) / Total number of city inhabitants
Environmental Quality	EMF Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of sites complying with WHO guidelines / Total number of sites] *100
	Noise Exposure	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants exposed to noise levels [LDEN (day-evening- night)] over 55 dB(A) / Total city inhabitants] *100
Education	Student ICT Access	Calculate as: [Students with classroom access to ICT facilities / Total number of students enrolled in schools] *100
	School Enrolment	Calculate as: [Number of students in primary and secondary levels in public and private schools / Total number of the school aged population] *100
	Higher Education Degrees	Calculate as: Number of city inhabitants holding at least one higher level education degree / One 100,000th of the city's population
	Adult Literacy	Calculate as: [Number of adult city inhabitants who are deemed to be literate / Total number of city inhabitants'] *100
Culture	Cultural Expenditure	Calculate as: Municipal expenditure on preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage (USD) / Total city operating budget (USD).

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Cultural Infrastructure	Calculate as: Number of cultural institutions / One 100,000th of the city's population.
Housing	Informal Settlements	Calculate as: [Number of people living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Expenditure on Housing	Calculate as: [Expenditure on Housing (USD) / Total household income (USD)] *100
Social Inclusion	Gender Income Equality	Calculate as: Average hourly earnings of female employees (USD) / Average hourly earnings of male employees (USD)
	Gini Coefficient	Calculate as: Area between 45 degree line and Lorenz curve / Entire area below 45 degree line.
	Poverty Share	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants living below the poverty line / Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Child Care Availability	Calculate as: [Number of day-care spots available for pre-school children / Total number of pre-school age children] *100
	Access to electricity	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to electricity / Total population] *100
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale
		Yes / No

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No
Multi-level governance	Municipal involvement-Financial support	Likert scale
	Smart city policy	Likert scale
	Supportive financing mechanisms	Yes / No
Scalability and replicability	Social compatibility	Likert scale
	Technical compatibility	Likert scale
	Ease of use for end users of the solution	Likert scale
	Trialability	Likert scale
	Advantages for end users	Likert scale
	Advantages for stakeholders	Likert scale
	Visibility of Results	Likert scale
		Likert scale

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Solution(s) to development issues	
	Effective co-ordination with other government bodies	Likert scale

Table 13: Specific KPIs assigned to Thessaloniki

	KPI	Measuring methodology
ICT Infrastructure	Household Internet Access	Calculate as: [Number of households with internet access / Total number of households] *100
	Fixed Broadband Subscriptions	Calculate as: [Number of fixed broadband subscriptions / Total number of households] *100
	Wireless Broadband Subscriptions	Calculate as: Number of wireless broadband subscriptions / one 100,000th of the city's population.
	Wireless Broadband Coverage	Calculate as: Area of city covered by mobile services (km2) / Total area of the city (km2). Each service should be reported on separately.
	Availability of WIFI in Public Areas	Calculate as: Total number of WIFI hotspots provided by the city administration (excluding commercial entities).
Employment	Creating and providing or supporting access to green and decent jobs for an inclusive and balanced workforce in companies and organizations	Yes / No.
	Retraining and re- and/or up-skilling workers for an inclusive and balanced workforce	Yes / No.
	Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed / Total city-related labor force] *100
	Youth Unemployment Rate	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related unemployed youth/ Total city-related youth labor force] *100
	Tourism Industry Employment	Calculate as: [Total number of city-related employees-Tourism Sector / Total city-related labor force] *100
	ICT Sector Employment	Calculate as: [Number of employees ICT sector / Number total city labor force] *100
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as:[Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m2) / Total area of public buildings (m2)] * 100. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings
		Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2)

Table 13: Specific KPIs assigned to Thessaloniki

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	/ Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitant
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitalized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements). --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: [Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr) / Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)] *100
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: [Total energy consumption from fossil fuels / Total energy consumption] * 100
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants

Table 13: Specific KPIs assigned to Thessaloniki

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m2)
Housing	Informal Settlements	Calculate as: [Number of people living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Expenditure on Housing	Calculate as: [Expenditure on Housing (USD) / Total household income (USD)] *100
Social Inclusion	Gender Income Equality	Calculate as: Average hourly earnings of female employees (USD) / Average hourly earnings of male employees (USD)
	Gini Coefficient	Calculate as: Area between 45 degree line and Lorenz curve / Entire area below 45 degree line
	Poverty Share	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants living below the poverty line / Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Child Care Availability	Calculate as: [Number of day-care spots available for pre-school children / Total number of pre-school age children] *100
	Access to electricity	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to electricity / Total population] *100
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale
	Balanced project team	Likert scale
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale
	Just transition planning	Likert scale

Table 13: Specific KPIs assigned to Thessaloniki

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No

Table 14: Specific KPIs assigned to Zagreb

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Transport	Diverse and affordable transport networks	Calculate as: Number of different modes of public transportation available (buses, trams, metro, etc.).
	Dynamic Public Transport Information	Calculate as:[Number of stops and stations with dynamic information available / Total number of stops and stations] *100
	Traffic Monitoring	Calculate as:[Length of major streets monitored by ICT (km) / Total length of major streets (km)] *100
	Intersection Control	Calculate as:[Number of intersections with adaptive traffic control / Total number of signal controlled intersections] * 100
	Public Transport Network	Calculate as: Length of public transport lines within city boundaries (km) (one way length) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Public Transport Network Convenience	Calculate as: [Total number of city inhabitants living within 0.5km of a public transport stop / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Bicycle Network	Calculate as: km of bicycle paths/lanes / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Transportation Mode Share	Calculate as:[Number of travellers using a specific transportation mode / Total number of travellers] *100 Report on modes: public transportation, personal vehicles, bicycles, walking, paratransit.
	Shared Bicycles	Calculate as: Number of shared bicycles available / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Shared Vehicles	Calculate as: Number of shared vehicles / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Low-Carbon Emission Passenger Vehicles	Calculate as: [Number of low emission vehicles registered (PHEV & EV) / Number of total vehicles] *100
	Non-polluting vehicles	Calculate as: % of non-polluting vehicles with respect to the total volume of vehicles.

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Public Sector	Comprehensive hazard and exposure mapping	Calculate as: The number of hazards included in the mapping (e.g., flooding, earthquakes, chemical spills).
	Open Data	Calculate as: $\frac{\text{Total number of open data sets published}}{\text{Total number of data sets}} * 100$
	e-Government	Calculate as: Number of public services available through online services.
Innovation	R & D Expenditure	Calculate as: $\frac{\text{R\&D expenditure (Euro)}}{\text{City GDP (Euro)}} * 100$
	Patents / start-ups	Calculate as: Total number of new patents issued to residents and organizations of the city / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises	Calculate as: $\frac{\text{Number of SMEs}}{\text{Total number of enterprises}} * 100$
	Diverse economic base	Calculate as: Inverse of the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) of industrial concentration, where lower values indicate greater diversification.
Buildings	Public Building Sustainability	Calculate as: $\frac{\text{Area of public buildings with certification to a recognized standard for ongoing building operations (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Total area of public buildings (m}^2\text{)}} * 100$. Report by Certification Scheme or percentage of the numbers of buildings

	KPI	Measuring methodology
	Integrated Building Management Systems in Public Buildings	Calculate as: [Floor Area of public buildings using ICT-based systems for integrated management in the city (m2) / Total floor number of public buildings in the cities (m2)] * 100 or percentage of the numbers
	Buildings with high energy efficiency rating	Calculate as: [Number of buildings with the highest energy efficiency rating / Total number of buildings evaluated] *100
Urban Planning	Pedestrian infrastructure	Calculate as: [Total area of pedestrian/car free zones / Total city area] *100
	Green areas	Calculate as: [Total green area/ Total city area] *100 or total green area / one 100,000th inhabitants
	Green Area Accessibility	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants living with 300m of a publicly accessible green space of at least 0.5ha / Number of city inhabitants] *100
	Urban Development and Spatial Planning	To collect the data for the measurement: Step 1: Identify city (in scope) Step 2: Deduce whether there is an urban plan for the city Step 3: Examine if urban plans contain all 5 sustainability principles/elements (if the plans are digitalized and on the web then consider using automated web queries with semantics to examine these elements). --> number: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Energy	Renewable Energy Consumption	Calculate as: [Total consumption of electricity from renewable sources (kWh/yr) / Total city electricity consumption (kWh/yr)] *100
	Electricity Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of electricity (kWh / year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Fossil fuel	Calculate as: [Total energy consumption from fossil fuels / Total energy consumption] * 100
	Residential Thermal Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total consumption of thermal energy (Gj/year) / Total number of city inhabitants.
	Public Building Energy Consumption	Calculate as: Total energy consumption by public buildings (ekWh/yr) / Total floor space of public buildings (m2).

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Health	Electronic Health Records	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants with electronic health records / Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Life Expectancy	Calculate as: Average number of years that a newborn is expected to live if current mortality rates continue to apply.
	Maternal Mortality Rate	Calculate as: Number of maternal deaths per year / One 100,000th of live births per year.
	Physicians	Calculate as: Number of general or specialized physicians working in the city (FTE) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	In-Patient Hospital Beds	Calculate as: Total number of in-patient hospital beds (public and private) / One 100,000th of the city's population.
	Health Insurance /Public Health Coverage	Calculate as: [Number of inhabitants covered by health insurance or a public health system / Total city inhabitants] *100
Housing	Informal Settlements	Calculate as: [Number of people living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing / Total city inhabitants] *100
	Expenditure on Housing	Calculate as: [Expenditure on Housing (USD) / Total household income (USD)] *100
Social Inclusion	Gender Income Equality	Calculate as: Average hourly earnings of female employees (USD) / Average hourly earnings of male employees (USD)
	Gini Coefficient	Calculate as: Area between 45 degree line and Lorenz curve / Entire area below 45 degree line.
	Poverty Share	Calculate as: [Number of city inhabitants living below the poverty line /Total number of city inhabitants] *100
	Child Care Availability	Calculate as: [Number of day-care spots available for pre-school children / Total number of pre-school age children] *100
	Access to electricity	Calculate as: [Number of people with access to electricity / Total population] *100

	KPI	Measuring methodology
Organization	Leadership	Likert scale.
	Balanced project team	Likert scale.
	Involvement of the city administration	Likert scale.
	Clear division of responsibility	Likert scale.
	Continued monitoring and reporting	Likert scale.
	Proactive corruption prevention	Likert scale.
	Just transition planning	Likert scale.
Community Involvement	Bottom-up or top-down initiative	Yes / No.
	Local community involvement in planning phase	Likert scale / number of participants.
	Local community involvement in implementation phase	Likert scale / number of participants.
	Participatory governance	Number of shares / number of participants.
	Social dialogue and stakeholder engagement in a just transition	Yes / No.